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Zfp3611 and Zfp3612 induction promotes luminal A fate choice during subtype selection.

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We conducted an expression screen using whole transcriptome technologies to identify genes important for the bifurcation event that separates the A and B luminal subtypes. We report identification of two zinc finger nuclear factors associated with the imprinting system, Zfp3611 and Zfp3612, as essential factors in selection of the A luminal subtype.